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Policy Intelligence Brief

Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities in the Just Transition: Pathways to Transformative Climate Finance From COP-30 Onwards

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Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	1
2. Problem and Relevance.....	2
3. Multilateral Climate Financing Framework Landscape	3
4. Evidence and Good Practices	4
5. Implementation Pathways and Recommendations.....	5
6. Annex 1: Executive Infographic	8

1. Executive Summary

Despite the unparalleled expansion of climate finance flows in the past years, reaching almost USD 1.3 trillion annually¹, Indigenous People and Local Communities (IPLCs) remain marginalized in terms of resource destination and decision-making power. This exclusion persists even though IPLCs are key actors for a more sustainable land governance across the globe.²

Around 20% of total net global Greenhouse Gases (GHG) emissions comes from the Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) sector, and half of it comes from Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) activities, mainly deforestation³. Since deforestation is dramatically reduced in IPLCs managed territories⁴, IPLCs become leading figures in the reduction of GHG emissions and in climate mitigation and adaptation in Brazil and abroad.

But, as Courtney McLaren and collaborators noted, “less than 1 percent of development assistance directed to forests, biodiversity, and climate between 2011 and 2020 went to supporting their [IPLCs] role in forest management

or securing their land tenure”⁵, despite the potential of IPLC territories for such projects⁶ and its guardianship of approximately 80% of the world’s biodiversity.⁷

Notably, restrictive eligibility criteria, limited access to financial institutions, and high transaction costs significantly constrain IPLC participation in climate finance, thereby reducing both the number and size of projects involving these communities and their impact. This *policy brief* is intended to give an up-to-date overview of IPLC climate finance, its main institutional features, as well as inclusive (focused on short-term *potential*) and transformative (focused on medium-term *necessary*) recommendations to policymakers. In light of COP-30, strengthening IPLC participation in climate finance mechanisms has become even more urgent.

“Climate justice depends on listening to and enabling those who protect the world’s ecosystems”

2. Problem and Relevance

Climate change is a global phenomenon, thought to negatively impact at least half of the world's population (3.3-3.6 billion people)⁸, nonetheless, its effects will not be evenly distributed across the globe. The impacts of climate change are disproportionate *between* countries⁹ and *within* them¹⁰, being more severe in poorer countries and among the poorest and most vulnerable populations of these countries. As historically marginalized communities within least-developed countries, IPLCs are and will be disproportionately affected by climate change.¹¹ This means thinking about climate finance in relation to IPLCs involves two main axes: adaptation within those communities, and mitigation, given their crucial role as major providers of ecosystem services.

Worldwide, IPLCs territories are estimated to provide directly and indirectly US\$ 1.16 trillion in ecosystem services annually, underpinning a considerable share of the global biodiversity and economy.¹² In Brazil, despite significant gaps in environmental protection laws, Indigenous Territories have historically maintained lower deforestation rates, largely due to their conservation practices and constitutionally recognized land rights.¹³

Improving IPLCs access to financial services might be an effective way to strengthen tenure and land rights, improve their resilience, and recognize IPLCs' role as key ecosystem services providers. But this involves dealing with a critical issue these groups face in the international financing structure, beyond the alarming fact that they are being underfinanced: the limited direct access to resources.

This problem relates to transaction costs — the long and complex path that resources take from financial institutions to IPLCs. A persistent barrier to effective IPLC finance is the limited capacity of many Indigenous organizations to receive direct funding from bilateral donors. At the same time, few donors are structured

to provide the technical support needed to prepare these organizations for direct access. As a result, most resources are channeled through intermediaries such as NGOs, multilateral bodies, international agencies, local and national governments or private consultancies, which can reduce the autonomy and impact of IPLC-led initiatives. Strengthening organizational capacity within IPLCs, alongside improving donor support mechanisms, is therefore essential for equitable and effective climate finance.

The actual amount of financial and non-financial resources that reach these communities is troublesome. The majority of IPLC-focused projects (83%) don't even formally name an Indigenous organization in their implementation description. An analysis of the Amazon Fund flows to IPLCs conducted by the Rainforest Foundation Norway also showed that less than half of the disbursements actually reached local organizations¹⁴. These elevated operational costs generate a "segregating spiral" and lead to inefficient resource allocation, ultimately undermining high-impact, IPLC-oriented initiatives. But they also present opportunities for "enabling" financing — targeted and collaborative technical support that could help unlock larger and more effective flows of finance.¹⁵

This issue also reflects a lack of proper democratic governance. Indigenous people have minimal influence over decision-making processes that could redesign financing frameworks. Nonetheless, the financing structure has shown some improvement over the past decade.

3. Multilateral Climate Financing Framework Landscape

Since the signing of the Paris Agreement at COP21, climate finance has reached a new institutional status. Funding has increased, and climate commitments have spread across the globe. However, IPLCs financing has only recently begun to show signs of being integrated into the broader climate financing framework. The New Collective Quantified Goal on Climate Finance (NCQG) signed at COP29 in Baku tripled financing goals to USD 300 billion annually, but there are still numerous gaps to be fulfilled. A decade after Paris, COP30 in Belém presents a historic opportunity to reframe Baku's pledges, scaling them up to USD 1.3 trillion. And without IPLCs, there is no fair or effective climate finance.

Several multilateral financial institutions are incorporating principles and policies directed toward IPLC financing. Despite the World Bank being the main provider, with multiple funds and programs, there are alternative and targeted institutions such as the Green Climate Fund (GCF), the Global Environment Facility (GEF), the Tenure Facility, as well as various private foundations¹⁶. Notably, the challenges related to direct access to resources, eligibility, and conditionalities remain significant.

The hosting of COP30 by Brazil creates an opportunity to lay new groundwork for IPLC finance. By instrumentalizing multilateral fora such as the G20 and BRICS, both under Brazil's current leadership, there is an intention and potential to integrate long-disconnected political-financial and technical-normative agendas, fostering financial structures that are both economically viable and socially fair. In this context, initiatives such as the Tropical Forest Forever Fund (TFFF) — expected to be announced in COP30 with an initial USD 1 billion commitment by Brazil and a minimum allocation of 20 percent for IPLCs — and the Brazil-

ian Investment Platform exemplify emerging mechanisms that could serve as reference models for inclusive climate finance.

Brazil's unique environmental characteristics, institutional experience, and strong civil-society engagement further reinforce this potential. The country has 119 million hectares of Indigenous Territories and *quilombola* communities¹⁷ — an extension that would make it the 25th largest country in the world — and stands as the major recipient of IPLC-related funding both in the region and globally.

In recent years, Indigenous leaders have taken part in Brazil's official COP delegations and have established themselves as key stakeholders through formal organizations such as the Articulation of Indigenous Peoples of Brazil (APIB). A unique outcome of this organizational process was the creation of the Brazilian Amazon Indigenous Fund (Podáali Fund, 2020) in 2020, recognized as the first Indigenous-led fund in Brazil. Now part of a global network of around 30 Indigenous-led funds, Podáali reflects the growing recognition of Indigenous leadership in climate finance — a trend reinforced by COP29's decision to increase Indigenous participation in carbon market designs. This initiative is one step toward overcoming the limited direct access and the conditionality-driven nature of resources available to IPLCs.

4. Evidence and Good Practices

Good financing practices and frameworks toward IPLCs must achieve two goals: a larger and stable share of disbursements, and strong democratic governance. Regarding resource practices, strengthening thematic and specialized financial institutions along the lines of Tenure Facility and the Amazon Fund, coupled with establishing a minimum allocation for IPLC projects, would help secure more stable, consistent, and direct financial flows for these communities and organizations. Traditional climate facilities and investment funds, such as FCPF, CIF, GEF, and GCF, only designate a fraction of their project budget to IPLCs. Amidst fragile international commitments, strong ideological shifts, and uncertainty, hybrid financing instruments — though far from ideal — can offer transitional solutions to reduce exposure to voluntary pledges, price instability (as in carbon markets), and nationally constrained incentives. Notably, both issues are being addressed by the TFFF proposal.

The second goal involves a more robust governance of IPLC in financial facilities and investment funds. The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) made a breakthrough by including indigenous peoples as full voting members. The aforementioned TFFF will have an Advisory Council of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities. Indigenous-led funds are also growing in number and projects.

This is one step closer to addressing the patent ontological differences in how ecosystems are valued and understood. While global finance tends to objectify them primarily as carbon stocks or as providers of measurable and monetizable environmental services, Indigenous peoples' connections to their territories are holistic, embedded in historical, cultural, and political relations.

The former relies on reactive, demand-driven

logics, whereas the latter reflects a relational, adaptive, and long-term guardianship perspective. Both issues, when combined, reveal an inherent contradiction: processes of “tokenization” and financial efficiency appear antithetical to the re-signification of ecosystems through a more holistic and sustainable lens.

In simpler words: financial instruments demand standardization, quantification, accountability, and market logic, while IPLCs' relationships with territories are relational, cultural, and not reducible to metrics. This poses challenges but also underscores opportunities for inclusive short-term and transformative medium-term changes.

5. Implementation Pathways and Recommendations

Considering both the urgency for tackling the shortcomings of the current climate finance framework applied to IPLCs and the need for structural reforms in the international climate financing architecture, this Brief proposes a two-stage recommendation strategy.

Stage one focuses on **inclusive, short-term recommendations**, designed with immediate, viable, and tangible solutions in order to promote short-term improvements. Stage two aims to showcase **structural, medium-term solutions** to tackle the wider architecture and governance challenges of the current climate finance model.

Because IPLCs play a major role in ecosystem services, we understand that good practices towards unlocking the access of these communities to international financing structures must take into account two pillars: (1) larger and more stable disbursements destined to IPLCs, with a strong leaning towards inclusive governance and training of the recipients to promote self-management, and (2) more robust participation of IPLCs on international climate finance institutions.

Having those two pillars as ideal reference points, our recommendations are the following

Inclusive, short-term recommendations	Transformative, medium-term recommendations
Implementing training programs on project and resource management and advocacy essentials to IPLCs	Creation of specific funds and facilities for IPLCs, with simplified rules for disbursement
Warrant the participation of IPLCs in national councils and UNFCCC platforms. Bodies such as the Local Communities and Indigenous Peoples Platform (LCIPP) already exist under the UNFCCC umbrella, and could be strengthened.	Redesign of the global climate finance architecture, making sure that IPLCs are recognized as direct beneficiaries and resource managers, not only as providers of ecosystem services. That includes international funds, Multilateral Development Banks (MDBs), and domestic frameworks.
Involve local leadership in the co-creation of financing criteria, aligning projects to local needs and specific realities.	Recognition of traditional knowledge as a strategic asset in the eligibility criteria of global funds, going beyond mere carbon metrics.
Utilize emergent mechanisms, such as the Tropical Forests Forever Facility (TFFF), which should be launched at COP-30, and estimates a minimum allocation of 20% of funds to IPLCs, as a reference for inclusive climate finance	Institutionalization of governance quotas in international funds, such as the GCF and the Adaptation Finance, for IPLCs. It is essential to warrant Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) in all decisions that may affect their cultures and territories.
	Developing hybrid mechanisms focused on IPLCs, such as fiduciary funds, impact financing, and venture philanthropy, specific for adaptation purposes.
	Promoting the alignment between climatic, racial, and territorial justice. Adaptation finance must prioritize more vulnerable populations.

Finally, we point out that our recommendations have taken into consideration the five priorities established by the COP-30 Circle of Finance Ministers Report on the Baku to Belém Roadmap to deliver on the USD 1.3 trillion expectation: (1) quantitative and qualitative expansion of concessional finance, (2) expansion of the role of Multilateral Development Banks, (3) structuring of domestic capacity and enabling environments to absorb and deploy increased flows, (4) mobilization of the private sector and (5) setting regulatory frameworks to support sustainable finance while maintaining financial stability¹⁸. The Baku–Belém Roadmap to 1.3T, launched on November 4th by the COP29 and COP30 Presidencies, sets out a medium-term plan to mobilize at least USD 1.3 trillion annually for developing countries by 2035. Structured around five action fronts — Replenishing, Rebalancing, Rechanneling, Revamping, and Reshaping (5Rs) — it seeks to expand concessional finance, ease debt burdens, mobilize private capital, and align financial systems with climate goals. Progress will be monitored through high-level ministerial dialogues and global stocktakes until 2029, as a “reference framework”.

For Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs), the Replenishing, Rebalancing, and Revamping pillars open new pathways for direct and equitable access to climate finance. Replenishing calls for scaled-up grants and concessional funds while addressing barriers such as lack of collateral and recognition. **Rebalancing** urges multilateral development banks to review policies regarding non-concessional lending and “high-risk” debt — one of the key gatekeeping practices identified in IPLC financing. **Revamping** promotes inclusive country platforms that could help integrate IPLCs in planning and investment processes. Together, these measures, should they be implemented, could create a viable and robust pathway for IPLCs within global financial governance, acknowledging their central and active role in driving a just and effective climate transition.

6. Annex 1: Executive Infographic

Baku: COP29

Countries concluded the long-awaited process of establishing a new collective quantified goal (NCQG): 1.3 trillion dollars annually of climate finance to developing countries by 2035 (Decision 1/CMA.6)

Indigenous People and Local Communities (IPLCs)

Despite their vast potential and stewardship of roughly 80% of global biodiversity, less than 1% of forest-, biodiversity-, and climate-related development assistance from 2011 to 2020 supported IPLC-related projects.

IPLC financing

Unlocking IPLC governance

But much is still needed to ensure meaningful IPLC participation and governance in financial mechanisms, expand direct access to resources, and strengthen the technical and organizational capacities required for “enabling” financing to flow effectively

Submissions and consultations

From February to March Parties and other stakeholders submitted 117 documents regarding their expectations to the Roadmap outcomes; from May to October the Presidency conducted multiple consultations, reinforced by the Bonn Climate Change Conference in June

Provisional Results

The COP30 Circle of Finance Ministers incorporated governance and a minimum allocation for IPLCs into its short to long term recommendations, while the TFFF aims to serve as a benchmark for IPLC finance.

Baku-Belém Roadmap

The Baku-Belém Roadmap to 1.3T outlines a medium-term strategy to mobilize USD 1.3 trillion annually by 2035 through its five action fronts — Replenishing, Rebalancing, Rechanneling, Revamping, and Reshaping (5Rs). For IPLCs, the Replenishing, Rebalancing, and Revamping pillars offer new avenues for direct and equitable access to climate finance, which —if implemented— could establish a more inclusive and just global financial framework.

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Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities in the Just Transition

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